

Northern Ireland Good Friday Agreement

Date Signed: 10 April, 1998

Accord Type: Comprehensive Peace Agreement

Country: United Kingdom

95.24

Implementation Score after 10 years

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PROVISIONS IN THIS ACCORD

Cease Fire

Powersharing Transitional Government

Constitutional Reform

Inter-ethnic/State Relations

Electoral/Political Party Reform

Decentralization/Federalism

Dispute Resolution Committee

Judiciary Reform

Police Reform

Demobilization

Disarmament

Reintegration

Prisoner Release

Paramilitary Groups

Human Rights

Right of Self-Determination

Citizenship Reform

Women's Rights

Education Reform

Official Language and Symbol

Minority Rights

Reparations

Economic and Social Development

Ratification Mechanism

Detailed Implementation Timeline

Independence Referendum

Review of Agreement

Verification/Monitoring Mechanism

Paramilitary Groups

Implementation Timeline

About this Provision

Strand Three: Security:

3. The Secretary of State will consult regularly on progress, and the response to any continuing paramilitary activity, with the Irish Government and the political parties, as appropriate.

Please always cite: ["Annualized implementation data on comprehensive intrastate peace accords, 1989–2012."](#) Madhav Joshi, Jason Michael Quinn, and Patrick M. Regan. *Journal of Peace Research* 52 (2015): 551-562.

